

BROKEN BENGAL

Tropes of Conviviality and Fracture in Bangla Fiction

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Abstract

This essay examines how Bangla fiction employs the trope of conviviality as a means to provide an affective understanding of the partition of Bengal. Of principal concern is how Bengali writers, regardless of their religious affiliation, insist upon the existence of a common Bengali across the religious divide. I open my essay with a brief historiographic introduction to the fracturing of Bengali society, contextualizing the backstories that are rarely fleshed out within Bangla fiction yet are elliptically present. Conviviality is the term I use to frame a common Bangla culture, and I explore the concept through Ivan Illich, Thomas Erikson and Tina Steiner. While conviviality is, moreover, applied to modern multicultural societies, I argue that it is also a valid concept for the plural society of pre-partition Bengal. I shall examine the dramatic structures employed which aid in the discovery of new perspectives on the societal fracture that occurred during the partition of Bengal. A phenomenological approach, I argue, is often used to represent this fracture. Bangla fiction seeks to represent the structures of experience as presented to an individual rather than being reflecting prior truths as presented through history. This concept is explained through Maurice Merleau-Ponty's understanding of the phenomenological world. I shall also draw attention to texts that narrate the existence of cross-class solidarity. By focusing on class instead of religion, I identify an alternative way to configure the trope of conviviality within Bangla literature. Finally, I examine how literature explores the loss of this syncretic Bengali culture through the specific trope of nostalgia. Here, I employ Svetlana Boym's understanding of the term and her distinction between reflective and restorative types. Regarding the former, reflective nostalgia acknowledges the imperfect process of remembrance, and I argue that Bangla literature employs this form of nostalgia, mediated through what Boym defines as "individual and cultural memory" (49).

Keywords

Bangla literature, conviviality, Hindu-Muslim divide, historiography, Partition of Bengal, reflective nostalgia

About the Author

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INTRODUCTION

The fracturing of Bengali society started with Lord Curzon's dividing of Bengal in 1905 and the establishment of a separate Muslim ward. One must take into account that, as Caroline Elkins bears witness to it, Bengal was the seat of the nascent national liberation movement within India and, for this reason, British liberal imperialism saw a division of Bengali society as a way to curtail a threat to its hegemony. In his speech in Dacca on February 18, 1904, Curzon assured that the partition of Bengal would, "invest the Mohammedans in Eastern Bengal with a unity which they have not enjoyed since the days of the old Mussulman Viceroys and kings" (Curzon qtd. in Sumit Sarkar 16). Whilst the creation of a separate Muslim ward failed, the idea of a separate Islamic state penetrated the collective consciousness of many ordinary Muslims, and the final partition of Bengal in 1947 was the result of the breakdown of mutual trust between Hindus and Muslims. By negotiating separately with the Muslim community, the colonial state invested new political meaning to what being a Muslim meant and this, effectively, changed the way Muslims saw themselves in relation to Hindus. Sumit Sarkar views this as a "deep imperialist design of 'divide and rule'" (11) which served to create a new set of antagonisms between Muslims and Hindus. What colonial politics in Bengal thus succeeded in doing was to motivate elites from both sides of the religious divide to manufactured religious identities as a means to piggyback their own political aspirations onto the social structures of local faith communities.

THE ANTECEDENTS OF FRACTURE

Historically, more than half of united Bengal was Muslim and the majority of this population was from East Bengal. Within this context, Ashgar Ali Engineer speaks of the existence of certain prejudices between the Muslim and Hindu religious communities (5). Rakesh Batabyal, however, argues that the level of antagonism that occurred during the first part of the twentieth century did not previously exist in Bengal (24). There is a tendency in Indian historiography to locate the seeds of fracture within the rise of a political Islam, fomented by colonial administrators. From here, Prabha Dixit purports that upper-class Muslims instrumentalized religious and cultural differences through a political doctrine of communalism which, in turn, provoked a rise in Hindu communalism (3-5, 56). We must, however, view Dixit's position in conjunction with how an upper caste urban Hindu class or *bhadralok* had performed a more successful assimilation to the colonial culture. The fact that nine-tenths of zamindaris² (landholdings) were held by Hindus, with

the landless peasants being mostly Muslims, points to a serious imbalance within Bengali society. In comparison to caste Hindus, Muslims fell behind in education and lost political leverage. They turned to communalism as a means of garnering power (Batabyal 24), and Bidyut Chakrabarty assures that “Capitalising on the disproportionate development between the two communities, the Muslim political forces strengthened their claims for a separate state” (36).

The rise of Muslim communalism must be viewed vis-à-vis the anti-colonial movement which first took root in Bengal. This was fundamentally an urban phenomenon orchestrated by the aforementioned *bhadralok* community who extended their political vision and influence beyond their natural hinterland to penetrate rural areas in Bengal. Swadeshi³, as a fundamental strategy of this anti-colonial movement, was very much Hindu in its organizational structure. Partha Chatterjee assures that Muslims did not identify in the same manner with the Swadeshi movement and had less reason to oppose administrative change in comparison to Hindus (227-28). Muslims had no access to education or employment within government services, and the establishing of a Muslim political body, as heralded by the nineteenth-century Bengali reformer Syed Ahmed, was conceived as a means to readdress this inequality.

That said, Rakesh Batabyal provides evidence as to how political Islam was predominately focused on a small body of upper-class Muslims which, by-and-large, represented a *middle*-class struggle to readdress the imbalances created by a colonial/capitalistic system (24). So as to garner power, this Bengali Muslim political elite, as Patricia A. Grossman establishes, was successful in constructing a separate Bengali Muslim identity “out of the violent symbols that cut across class and religious divisions” (3). Prior to the late nineteenth century, Bengali Muslims did not affiliate with a larger, North Indian identity, nor did they perceive themselves as being in conflict with Bengali Hindus. Sarkar establishes how an alien Wahhabis and Faraizis ideology entered Bengal and commenced to violently denounce polytheism amongst Muslim peasants and to purify the local Islamic culture of its syncretic traces. Nandy considers that this Islamic fundamentalism was not concerned with the living Muslim but, on the contrary, fomented “idealized concepts of Islam to which the Muslim must conform” (162-63).

The emergence of this Islamic identity, thus, played a fundamental part in the 1946 communal riots in Calcutta which Bidyut Chakrabarty, Grossman, and Batabyal all see as having created a template for future Partition violence across India. Bidyut Chakrabarty specifically draws attention to how Huseyn Shaheed Suhrawardy, by tapping into a Muslim malcontent, called for a Direct Action Day, on July 1946, Calcutta, and the then Chief Commissioner, through his use of inflammatory language and references to *jihad*, sparked off communal riots

in the city (65-72). As a result, this instrumentalization of a legitimate Muslim dissensus gave birth to a fratricidal energy, which quickly found its roots in the neighboring areas of Noakhali and Tippera. Particularly in Noakhali, violence was marked by widespread atrocities, including mass killings, arson, looting, and forced conversions. The Noakhali riots had a significant impact on communal relations in Bengal and contributed to an atmosphere of fear and mistrust between the two communities. The rumors of these violent outbursts spread beyond the borders of Bengal to much of Northern India. Yasmin Khan gives witness to a “programme of well-planned ethnic cleansing” (68) in Noakhali where the Muslim League employed strongmen (former members of the Muslim League National Guard and many of whom were not from the region) to instill terror, whilst Golam Sarwar, the elected Muslim league politician, created a toxic atmosphere by insisting that “all non-Muslims should be converted” (69).

Due to colonial communal awards, Hindus lost power in provincial Bengali institutions from the 1930s onwards. The Hindu hegemony, thus, needed to bump up its electoral base, and this was effectuated by promoting a campaign of *shuddi* (purification) and *sangathan* (mobilization) amongst the Namasudras of North Bengal and Rajbangshis and Santals of East Bengal (Batabyal 295). As with the Muslim elite, one can safely surmise that a caste Hindu ideology held little real interest in the socio-economic plight of this underclass, yet the inclusion of “untouchable” classes within the fold of Hinduism became a strategy to avoid solidarity between the Namasudras and a disenfranchised Muslim population. Kaiser Haq, for example, draws attention to how certain Scheduled Castes groups of East Bengal coalesced around the figure of Jogendra Nath Mandal and formed an alliance with the Muslim League⁴ (502). This is something that the *bhadralok* hegemony wanted to avoid at all costs.

Resistance to colonial power, as put forth by Bengali Hindu intellectuals such as Swami Vivekananda and Sri Aurobindo was mediated through Hinduism. Within a large proportion of their writings, all things Hindu became metonymic representations of the gestating nation, which meant, as Peter Heehs assures in “Bengali Religious Nationalism”, that Muslims did not identify in the same way with the Indian nationalist movement (122). Gyanendra Pandey, in this light, establishes how the *bhadralok* community had acquired a status of privilege that was equated with the general, whilst all other communities—especially Muslims—were simply marginalized (50). The homogenizing of all forms of national belonging through Hinduism had, Heehs argues in the same article, an ideological parallel with how Russian Slavophilism fused Orthodoxy and nationalism (124)⁵. This ideology alienated many middle-class Muslims from a possible affiliation with Indian national identity, and this rejection created a filtering down effect to the lower strata of Muslim society.

A final question one must pose is if united Bengal was a plural society—a space where distinct ethnic groups lived separately but in close proximity with each other—or if it constituted a pluralistic society with a high level of cross-cultural integration. There existed a strong inter-communal relation between Hindus and Muslims yet, through Sarkar, Engineer, and Chatterjee, I propose that the latter plural model of cohabitation, which pre-dates colonial interventions, is the more fitting classification. As Leo Kuper indicates, plural societies can often implode under the stress of imperial policies of interference and manipulations (57) and, in the case of Bengal, the hurried process of decolonization brought about unknown levels of violence between Hindus and Muslims. The ensuing violence of Partition was not the result of century-old animosities but rather “a planned political act, a tool of political mobilization used to change popular perceptions of group identification” (Grossman 3). This violence, however, was not on the cataclysmic scale of the Punjab, and the movement of populations across the newly demarcated Radcliff Line in Bengal was a more long-drawn-out process. Haq suggests that a large-scale communal violence did not take place in Bengal due to “the benign influence of a shared syncretistic cultural heritage Bengal” (502). As Kabir assures, Bengal “did not experience the surgical cut of a clean transfer of population” (174), and there was a continual movement of populations, primarily from east to West Bengal⁶, which Debjani Sengupta describes as having moved “sometimes in trickles, and sometimes like tidal waves” (232).

DISCOVERING CONVIVIALITY IN BANGLA FICTION

All Bangla literary productions on Partition, regardless of the religious affiliations of the authors in question, bear witness to a shared Bangla culture and narrate the tragic consequences of its destruction. One of the defining aspects of Bangla literature regarding Partition seeks to deconstruct colonial discourses that purport an incommensurable difference between Hindus and Muslims. Regarding day-to-day relationships, I employ the term “conviviality” as a way of defining the coexistence between Hindus and Muslims.

The spirit of conviviality, and the tragic fracturing of Bangla society, is literature’s primary focus, and within its narratives there is a sense of those lost opportunities as regards the possibilities of a plural and united Bengal. In his *Tools for Conviviality*, Ivan Illich establishes conviviality as a means of empowerment where people acquire agency and autonomy through convivial interactions rather than being hindered by institutions that shape their lives for them. I am aware that this idea of

conviviality is employed, moreover, within a contemporary multicultural context, a salient example being Paul Gilroy's *After Empire: Melancholia or Convivial Culture?* which argues for a convivial culture of shared spaces and dialogue among diverse communities, which becomes a way for these cultures to coexist harmoniously and to transcend the divisive legacies of empire. For example, Thomas Hylland Eriksen's "Creolisation as a Recipe for Conviviality," through a reading of cultural theorists such as Homi Bhabha, Stuart Hall, James Clifford, etc., situates Mauritius creole culture as a paradigm of this conception of conviviality (44). Tina Steiner examines the strategies whereby societies go beyond mere tolerance so as to live with otherness, whereby conviviality undoes racism and inequality. Steiner's point of departure is located through her close reading of Gilroy's *After Empire* which brings the author to explore, on the one hand, "how and under what conditions do people create patterns of human flourishing that privilege mutuality and interconnectedness" (6) and, on the other hand, how one may establish "convivial relation with others in the face of inevitable suffering and asymmetrical power" (10). I feel that this contemporary model of conviviality is something that could have been explored within a united Bengal were it not for a sustained imperial violence that fomented fracture.

One of the ways in which Bangla fiction narrates the breaking down of conviviality is through a phenomenological approach. While these kinds of narratives may not always emphasize first-person perspectives, they seek an understanding of the structures of experience as presented to an individual rather than providing a more dominant historiographic focus. If we take Maurice Merleau-Ponty's understanding of the phenomenological world as "not the making explicit of a prior being, but rather the founding of being" (xxxiv), then the phenomenological perspective in Bangla Partition literature is not a reflection of a prior truth (historiography), but rather the actualization of a truth.

Edmund Husserl, in his work *Ideas: General Introduction to Pure Phenomenology*, contrasts the noema (the object) with the noesis, which is defined as the act or process of consciousness directing its attention toward the noema. Within Bangla fiction, there is a narrative tendency towards individuals directing their consciousness towards the phenomena of rupture and violence (noesis) rather than authorial descriptions of Partition (noema). Atin Bandyopadhyay's "Infidel," originally titled "Kafir" and set in East Bengal, is a good example of this. The subjective, lived experience of fracture and the ensuing violence is derived from a narrative with an affective locus. When the narrator describes how the villagers are "possessed only by an intense hatred and a mad drive to kill, [that] seemed to engulf the whole region like an evil shadow" (169), the reader experiences this moment from a phenomenological perspective. By internally focalizing on Hashim, a Muslim farmer, communal violence is narrated as a phenomenon rather than

an object of study. A common trope in Bangla partition fiction has Hashim give refuge to his Hindu neighbor, Paran, during a riot, by dressing him as a Muslim. This intimate friendship between a Hindi and a Muslim serves to focalize the more abstract concept of conviviality within the plot.

When Paran is slain by a group of men, we come to experience how larger political realities have encroached upon the rural setting to crush a syncretic sense of belonging. Going against the new orthodoxies of ethnic exclusivism is marked as transgressive and, in Hashim's case, he is accused by his own people of being a *kafir* (a derogatory term used for Hindus). Unable to adapt to this new mindset, Hasim descends into madness, motivated by the collapse of the old cultural bonds in East Bengal. The story can thus be seen as a microcosmic representation of how communalist conflict affects the lives of ordinary people evident, in this case, in the way in which Muslims were intoxicated by the hate speeches of mid-level politicians and were driven to commit violence against Hindus. Bandyopadhyay's short story, thus, provides readers with an affective register that is, often time, absent within the historiography of the Partition of Bengal. In this light, Terri Tomsy speaks of a prevailing "absence of affect" within official historical documentation on Partition and of a disengaged tone that fails to register human emotions such as loss, pain, or despair (59). My claim is that the majority of Bangla literary texts privilege affective responses to Partition over historiographic detail.

How the introduction of an alien religious dogma in Bengal drove a wedge between local religious communities is also narrated in Pratibha Basu's "Flotsam and Jetsam", originally entitled "Dukulhara." This is achieved through the story of Bindubastini, a widow who visits Jamir, the local mullah, in search of advice as regards her future in East Bengal. The narrator tells us that "life had taught her that she had nothing whatsoever to fear from Muslims" (34), yet, in relation to our earlier discussion on the incursion of an alien Wahhabis and Faraizis ideology in Bengal, Jamir informs Bindubastini that "renowned mullahs have come to our country from outside. They ask us to kill, ransack houses and, [...] provoke us to take all the women regardless of age" (35). Even the respected *maulvis*, the teacher of Islamic law who is steeped in the transversal Bengal culture, finds himself forced to endorse an imposed ideology of ethnic cleansing against his lifetime neighbors. As a result, Bindubastini is forced to leave her native East Bengal under the local mullah's advice that she is no longer safe—which operates as a coded word for rape. However, when Bindubastini arrives as a refugee to an ashram in West Bengal with her daughter-in-law, an upper-caste Hindu forces her daughter-in-law into prostitution. Deciding that Bindubastini's body is too old to be profitable, the upper-caste Hindu kills her and leaves her body to rot at the side of the road. The subversive quality of Basu's story is palpable in how it juxtaposes the affective bonds between Bindubastini and the *maulvis*. The violent imposition of new and

violent identity markers, in this case a Wahhabis culture, destroys the syncretic local culture.

An additional story of relevance is by Mahasweta Devi, born into Brahmin family, who dedicated much of her life to the empowerment of the tribal peoples of West Bengal. Her short story “Of Ram and Rahim”, originally titled “Ram Rahimer Katha,” examines how populations that fell outside of the hegemonic constructs of Hindu identity, fomented by Partition politics, suffered from a violence they themselves had never taken part in. As with “Infidel” and “Flotsam and Jetsam,” the text adopts a similar phenomenological approach through the story’s protagonist, Sajumoni, who observes with horror how her caste Hindu neighbors are “calling the goddess Kali and chopping off the heads of refugees with the large sacrificial knife” (374). The short story ends with her son, Rahmin, being butchered at a neighboring market by Muslims whilst selling puffed rice to survive. Previously, in a textual aside, the reader is told that “Their god [Hindu] meant the local Shitala or Panchu Thakur, [and] by native land or India, they understood Hetampur” (374-5). This quotation points to the constructed nature of Hindu universalism which I previously discussed through the writings of Swami Vivekananda and Sri Aurobindo. Rahmin’s violent death, simply because he is a Hindu, dramatizes how the politicization of local religious identities coerces a casteless class into scenarios of communal violence. Through the privileged point of view of Sajumoni, the reader vicariously gains lived experience into how a casteless Bengali underclass is caught within a double bind, being both subjected to the epistemic violence of the everyday through a rigid caste system, and becoming trapped within the fratricidal violence of Partition.

THE OTHER TIMES OF PARTITION

Sunanda Sirdar’s *A Life Long Ago*, originally entitled *Dayamoyeer Katha*, is the only memoir dealt with in this essay. The text presents a distinct structure in that it purports the narrativization of Partition without the standard dramatic resources employed in fiction. Sarbani Banerjee assures that *A Life Long Ago* steps outside of a *bhadralok* world-view to produce “a more egalitarian and complex understanding” (4) of Partition, and provides us with “an alternative to the *bhadramahila* [a Bengali term which refers to a woman of virtue, and moral standing] ethos” (5). While *A Life Long Ago* is told from the perspective of an upper-caste Hindu woman, its narrative thrust does not speak from a position of caste privilege.

Banerjee, in this light, problematizes the domination of East Bengali *bhadralok* immigrant memory in works such as Jyotirmoyee Devi's *The River Churning: A Partition Novel*, originally titled *Epar Ganga Opar Ganga*, and considers that such cultural productions "propounded elitist truisms to the detriment of the non-bhadra refugees' representations" (4). *The River Churning*, although containing certain autobiographical elements, is a work of fiction. Its principal concern is of caste Hindu anxiety towards contamination, focalized through the character of Sutara who is taken in and cared for by Tamij Saheb and his family when her parents are killed during the surge of communal violence. On the insistence of her extended family, she abandons her native village in East Bengal and joins them in Calcutta. Sutara, however, is ostracized due to her extended contact with Muslims and, due to her condition of contamination, is forced to internalize and suppress her feelings of rejection which augments her sense of melancholy at being exiled from East Bengal and its culture. The text, however, fails to engage with the complex nature of Partition beyond a female *bhadralok* perspective which, while valid, does not render the other instances of fracture.

One of *A Life Long Ago's* strengths is that it provides the reader with a singular insight into the local and syncretic culture of East Bengal from outside a caste Hindu perspective. Sunanda Sirdar did not leave her native East Bengal until the late 1950s, which, in itself, draws attention to how the movement of a Hindu population from East Bengal to West Bengal was a long-drawn-out process when compared to the partition of the Punjab. The abstract concept of migration is depicted through neighbors leaving Dighpait (Sirdar's birthplace) on bullock carts whilst "howling and weeping" (12). The narrator defines this abandoning of Dighpait as a cosmological loss, and the memoir's central theme, in this respect, is the reconstruction of the rural world of East Bengal from the locus of exile.

The principal focus within *udvastu* (refugee) memoirs is how being forced out of one's ancestral land leaves an indelible trace upon consciousness. Paushali Chakrabarty identifies how refugees from East Bengal tend to evoke images of a rural idyll and filter out the complexities of daily life (150). Examining *A Life Long Ago* from this perspective, one can detect a certain idealization as regards the evoking of this past yet, on the whole, the text is nuanced and realistic in its portrait of rural post-Partition East Bengal.

Regarding the archetypal trope of a common Bangla culture, Sirdar's memoir speaks of the intimate relationship between the young Daya (the stand-in for Sunanda Sirdar), and the Muslim manservant, Dada. The story's melancholic tone is informed by the narrator's sense of guilt at having abandoned Dada, having referred to him as "the person I depended upon most, throughout my childhood" (3). This imprint remains with Daya her whole life, and the focalizing of this affect

through their relationship symbolizes the bigger loss of intimacy between Hindus and Muslims: “Despite all my attempts to block out memories of him [Dada], I have remained connected to Dada through strong, invisible bonds” (3).

Local color is also employed to create a tableau of this common culture, most notably through the story of Majam Sheikh who, although illiterate, walks miles on an empty stomach to listen to a reciting of the Qu’ran or the Urdu epic of *Sirhi-Farhad* (3). There is, however, a marked silencing within *A Life Long Ago* as regards Partition violence. No reason is offered as to why the local Hindu families are leaving Dighpait for West Bengal and, contrary to Bandyopadhyay’s “Infidel,” the reader never comes to know if communal violence has assailed Dighpait.

By contrast, the text prefers to focus on other forms of quotidian conflict that affect social harmony. One way in which this is performed is through the aspect of Hindu exceptionalism. Food, and the codes that govern it, becomes the specific trope that the text use to display conflict. It is through these food rituals that we see how the discriminatory acts of caste Hinduism discourage social harmony and thwart inclusivity. The first example that the text offers is through Parul’s wedding where we see how a Hindu sense of exceptionalism creates ill-feeling amongst middle-class Muslims. At the celebration, the Brahmins and the Kayasthas are seated in the inner courtyard, the Kaivatras, the weavers and the washermen in the outer court, whilst the Muslims are obliged to sit outside the house. This belittlement, which the narrator identifies as creating societal rupture, is amplified in the memoir through the story of a fish that the Muslim, Sadi kaka, keeps in his pond in anticipation of one day receiving Daya’s father at a food celebration. Daya’s family are now set to leave for West Bengal, and Sadi kaka realizes that Aba will never accept sharing a meal with him due to caste Hindu pollution anxieties. As a final gesture, Sadi kaka bequeaths the fish to Daya’s father so that the family can eat it on their own. When the narrator observes how, “The old fish thrashed about in our yard and finally gave up the ghost, a testimony to the attachment, pain and sorrow that friendship brings” (163-4), she symbolically references how the pollution anxiety and their ingrained sense of entitlement of caste Hindus sowed the seeds of discontent and dissent amongst Muslims and fueled the rifts of Partition.

Sirdar’s memoir also bears witness to the paradigm shift that post-Independence brought about within the Muslim population. The narrator speaks about the plight of what are termed as “soil-lickers” (3), a rural Muslim underclass who held servant bond contracts with the Hindu zamindaris in East Bengal. The text focalizes this through the harsh negotiations between Majam and Mejokarta, the entrepreneurial Muslim who has taken over the business of the Hindu, Naresh Karmakar. The text draws attention to how a new Muslim elite, who profited from the acquisition of Hindu lands for a song, come to occupy the role of the old zamindari. Majam pleads

with Mejokarta to honor the old sharecropping agreements, yet Mejokarta's reply is "[...] if you [Majam] farm with my plough and oxen, you won't be entitled to half the crop. Get this clear" (8). The conditions that Mejokarta offer are even worse than those already in place under the old Hindu landowners and, here, Sardar bears witness to how a new comprador Muslim class is unconcerned with the plight of the Muslim peasants who had become destitute and are now starving.

Fracture within Bengal cannot solely be seen through the lens of the monolithic Hindu-Muslim divide. Subhoranjan Dasgupta, a Kolkata-born intellectual formed within a Marxist and neo-Marxist tradition, provides a timely deconstruction of this binary through the question of land rights in rural Bengal. He specifically references the *Tebhaga* movement⁷ which fought for the reduction of the landless *Bargadars'* (sharecropper) tithes to their Hindu and Muslim landlords. Both Congress and the Muslim League, Dasgupta argues, actively thwarted this movement while Partition, "was designed to facilitate the speedy ascent of a jotedar [landed wealthy peasants], who stepped into the shoes of the Hindu zamindar and persisted with the same tyranny" (35). This middle-class Muslim oligarchy thus garnered new authority and were "no less apathetic than the Hindus towards the exploited who were Muslims" (34). Nitish Sengupta assures that "the [Muslim] League was able to give it [*Tebhaga*] a communal-nationalist slant" (208), whilst the Muslim League employed the language of *Tebhaga*, assuring their Muslim support-base that "the land will belong to the tiller in the Islamic paradise" (37). Post-independent realities in East Bengal revealed that behind the nationalistic discourses that fueled Partition lay a calculated class collusion from both sides of the religious divide.

Akhtaruzzaman Elias's novel *Khwabnama*⁸ central theme deals with the *Tebhaga* movement. Despite belonging to an elite social group within partitioned Bengal (his father, Badiuzzaman Muhammad Elias, served as the Parliamentary Secretary of the Muslim League) Dasgupta assures that, "he [Akhtaruzzaman Elias] could never accept the division of Bengal" (33). *Khwabnama* narrates the fracturing of a common Bangla culture and, in particular, draws attention to what Dasgupta refers to as the "treachery" of the Muslim League who, whilst "shedding copious tears over the fate of Muslim peasants oppressed by Hindu zamindars," were impervious to their demands (34). Sengupta, in *The Partition of Bengal*, situates *Khwabnama* within "a critique of the national liberation paradigm" (208) and considers Elias's reading of the instrumentalization of the *Tebhaga* to be "historically quite sound" (219). The narrative point of view in *Khwabnama* employs both a historiographic approach whereby the socio-political implications *Tebhaga* are fleshed out by the narrator, and a phenomenological approach which represents the thwarting of *Tebhaga* through the lived experience of the Bengali peasant.

Criticism of the Muslim League is achieved through the narrative voice of Tamiz who realizes that the League has no wish to implement the demands of the peasant revolt. Dasgupta views the central issue in *Khwabnama* as the vanquishing of “this defiant agrarian revolt [that] invoke[s] the scenario of true redemption” (36), and an important consideration here is the role The Communist Party of India (CPI) played in mobilizing peasants and sharecroppers to cohere around the *Tebhaga* movement. Debal K. SinghaRoy speaks of how the CPI formulated the demands of the *Tebhaga* movement and built alliances with other peasant organizations to strengthen the movement (54-54). In contrast with the *Tebhaga*’s progressive energy, *Khwabnama* centres its attention on how the Muslim League viewed the CPI as a threat to its hegemony and thus appropriated the movement for its own ends. Quoting directly from *Khwabnama*, we can see through the inner focalization of politician Ismail Husain’s thoughts that

He [Ismail] was happy that the young men who had worked with the communists had joined the League. [...] if the party couldn’t hold on to these young workers they were bound to join the communists again. (199)

Elias’s narrator draws our attention to how the Muslim League micromanaged the complexities of the agrarian world to its own ends, and the section in the novel regarding the unnamed vagrant who moves around with the leaders of the *Tebhaga* movement and holds certain sway over the farmers is a point in hand. Ismail is described as being “in a quandary over the best course of action involving the absconding peasant-cum-singer” (205). Having managed “to organize the people in the area between Shaorapara and the western bank of the Jomuna, on the other side of the Bangali river” (205), he needs to measure his actions carefully regarding this vagabond. Ismail understands that he must continually “face the brunt [...] from the party leaders, who didn’t realize that unless these people [the aadhiars/ rural underclass] were molycoddled they would all defect to the red flag party” (206). For this reason, he looks for ways of coopting the vagrant which would mean “securing the support of the aadhiars” (206).

Khwabnama is judicious in its treatment of societal fracture, and it gives witness to how a bhadralok hegemony also preferred a partitioning of Bengal over a ceding of power to the Muslim League. Toward the end of the novel, characters move aimlessly around rural Bengal, hoping to find a location where *Tebhaga* might be implemented. Memories of “Nobabganj or Nachol or Thakurgaon or some such place the tebhaga protesters had scattered everywhere when beaten up by the police” (543) are still prevalent. For people like Tamiz

If the tebhaga system was established there [Thakurgaon] he [Tami] would surely find some land to sharecrop on. With his share of the harvest he would release his own house and land. (544)

The jotedar-ashraf⁹ were not interested in *Tebhaga* becoming a reality and were more invested in the establishment of India and Pakistan. *Tebhaga*, thus, becomes the true lost dream of an underclass, as represented through the characters of Satish Mokhtar or Tamis, rather than the abstract concept nationhood that does not touch their lives in any meaningful way. Much of the Bangla literary tradition is concerned with the idea that the religious nationalist discourses that emerged during the time of Partition had delivered false expectations as regards the lives of ordinary people. Fracture is typically configured as happening across the Hindu-Muslim divide, yet fiction uncovers the other times of Partition when class played a more decisive role. This, in turn, feeds into the trope of conviviality in that a subaltern group, despite its religious affiliation, realistically had more emotional connections with the underclass from the so-called opposite side of the religious divide. I shall now provide examples of the various literary texts that deal with this issue.

Satinath Bhaduri (also known by his literary pseudonym, Chitra Gupta) was both a politician and writer. Barnita Bagchi identifies a utopian energy in Bhaduri's novel *Dhorai Charit* which, through intertextuality with the Hindu epic, *Ramayana*, situates Dhorai, a member of the Tatma (weaver) community, as a stand-in for Ram, the upper-caste king of the Ramayana. Through the premise that "Congress members, manipulate anti-colonial politics to further their own power and profit" (Bagchi 16), Bhaduri creates a vision of an idealized Bengali society free from the manipulations of caste/class privilege. By contrast, Bhaduri's short "The Champion of the People", originally titled "Gananayak," dramatizes the pernicious manipulations of this elite group and how, once Partition became a reality, they maintained their privileges. Set in the district of Gopalpur, West Bengal, the story's narrator insists that, despite Partition violence, an ethos of plurality within Bengali society had been maintained: "The twisted rumours [that] spread from Calcutta, Bihar -and Noakhali last year had cut deep, [...] the scars were soon covered" (249). This is juxtaposed with how an unscrupulous comprador class from both sides of the religious divide manipulated the agitation of Partition for its own ends. The Muslim *ijaradar* (revenue farmer), Haji Sahih, for example, uses Partition politics to manipulate the price of grain and, furthermore, levels a faith-tax at the depot where this grain is sold. The local Hindu landowner, Munimiji, also looks to Partition for personal gain by appropriating the empty lands of Purnea (which will fall within India) as a fresh source of future revenue despite the fact that the local Hindu population "had scorned the land west of the Nagar, [river] as a malaria pit" (266). As a critique on partisan politics, Bhaduri, parodies the constructed

nature of national identities through Munimiji's side-line activity of selling the new national flags to both Hindu and Muslim populations. When it comes to light that a section of the area will no longer fall to Pakistan, he retrieves the flags he has sold the Muslim population and proceeds to re-sell them at a further date.

Nabendu Ghosh's "The Saviour", originally entitled "Traankarta," echoes these political manipulations by narrating how a Bengali underclass was duped into violent confrontation with a religious other. Set near Bhabanipur, Western Bengal, the narrative employs the *mise-en-scene* of a middle-class neighborhood from where its residents observe a Dantesque scene of mutilated bodies from a safe distance. In the face of this ensuing communal violence, the *doms*, a community of excluded non-caste Hindus, are coopted by the *bhadralok* community with cheap liquor and holiday sweets to serve as buffers against the marauding Muslims. Despite the fact that they are not allowed to enter the local temple due to pollution rites, they defend Shiva with their lives against the attacks, whilst the Dalit hero, Jhogru, dies in the melee, "because people like Jhogru were always born to save the likes of Mr. Bose [the stand-in for class hegemony]" (143).

Manikuntala Sen provides historical testimony to how the Muslim league also provoked communal violence in Bengal as a means to gain political leverage (55-57). In the short story, "Insignificance," by the same author, Nabendu Ghosh, provides a mirror image of this *bhadralok* cynicism through an examining of how the Muslim league actively dynamited cross-religious class solidarity by instigating a disaffected Muslim youth towards violence against Hindus. The narrator in "Insignificance" observes that, "They [The Muslim League] were handing over shining knives to young Muslim men in order to safeguard their own narrow interests" (118), while "The noble Indian ministers had tried to neutralize their strike by trying to instigate the average Muslim youth into communal violence" (122). "Insignificance" is set within the 1945-1946 Calcutta Tram Way Workers' Strike and references what the author saw as a cross-religious class movement that questioned the discourses of incommensurable cultural difference that Partition politics generated. When the protagonist Aziz concludes that, "They are thinking of Pakistan and Hindustan. [...] But we will remain exactly as we are" (120), one finds a collapsing of the colonial and the postcolonial through the continuum of the underclass condition.

I have already referenced how Bangla fiction employs the trope of friendship between a Hindu and a Muslim as a way to comment on the constructed nature of the communal divide between these communities. Manik Bandyopadhyay's "The Ledger," originally entitled "Khatian," explores this trope through the story of two friends, and the story opens up during a communal riot, with one of the men trapped in his friend's house. A mob has learned of the presence of this man and have come "in search of his blood" (145). As a dramatical device present in much

Bangla fiction, a Muslim man saves a Hindu's life (or vice-versa) and, by doing so, risks his own life by putting friendship before religious partisanship. Nonetheless, something has already shifted in the relationship between the two men and here Bandyopadhyay explores how class solidarity becomes mired by the manipulations of political affiliation through religion.

The friendship that had developed from working together in the same factory, and the camaraderie they had shared even till the other day, while walking shoulder to shoulder at a protest march and then coming out victorious, seemed to have received a sudden jolt. (146)

The following day both men arrive at the factory where they work only to find that they are amongst the forty men who have lost their jobs. One assumes that this is a reprisal for having participated in class action. Both the Hindu and the Muslim men are amongst those arrested by the police for disobeying Section 144¹⁰, and as they are being taken away in a police truck, one of the men says to his friend, "just say that neither you nor I have caste. You are poor and so am I. We belong to the poor community" (150). The fact that the religion of both men is never specifically mentioned in the text is important. This narrative reticence gives force to the idea of religious affiliations within the Bengal of Partition were, often time, artificial constructs in comparison to the real suffering of the underclass. "The Ledger," in this sense, dramatizes how a broader class solidarity suffered from the instrumentalization of religious identities and actually worked against the interests of a Bengali underclass.

CODIFYING THE LOSS OF CONVIVIALITY THROUGH NOSTALGIA

I shall now look at how literature explores the loss of conviviality in Bengal through the trope of nostalgia. In many texts, one can find narrative perspectives that dwell upon those cross-communal affective connections that were severed by the event of Partition. Much Bangla fiction contains a pervading nostalgia regarding the fracturing of a syncretic Bengali culture. Before proceeding to explore how different texts produce this nostalgic tone, I shall turn to Svetlana Boym's *The Future of Nostalgia* which distinguishes between reflective and restorative types of nostalgia. Restorative nostalgia, Boym asserts, "stresses *nostos* and attempts a transhistorical reconstruction of the lost home" (xviii), and is employed in nationalist revivals to "engage in the antimodern myth-making of history by means of a return to national symbols and myths" (41). Reflective nostalgia, on the contrary, "thrives in *algia*, the

longing, [...] dwells on the ambivalences of human longing [...] [and] can present an ethical and creative challenge” (xviii). One of the salient differences between the former and the latter is that, whilst restorative nostalgia sees itself as a truth gleaned from tradition, reflective nostalgia acknowledges the imperfect process of remembrance. Bangla literature, I contend, employs a reflective form of nostalgia, mediated through what Boym defines as “individual and cultural memory” (49).

Ritwik Ghatak’s “The Road,” originally titled “Sadak,” is a fine example of how Bangla texts use this reflective nostalgia as a creative response to the complexities generated by the upheaval of Partition. Two young men have come to visit their friend, Israel, at a slum that has recently suffered communal rioting. The specific location is not specified, and the only reference the reader is provided with is Park Circus refugee camp where Israel’s son, Emad, died of cholera. Likewise, the religious affiliation of the characters is not specified, yet, through inference, we can ascertain that Israel is Muslim and his two friends are Hindus.

The focal point of the story is how the two friends become witnesses to the uncanny bond that forms between Israel and a Hindu refugee who now occupies his home. Israel’s anger at being forced out of his own home and facing the prospect of leaving for East Bengal transmutes into an empathy for the old Hindu lady with whom he shares the trauma of displacement. Both Israel and the Hindu lady use nostalgia as a means to establish a connection with the past that has now been vanquished by Partition. In the case of Israel, the reader can perceive this through the memories of his son, Emad, whose paintings still hang on the walls of his home where the Hindu lady now resides. In a gesture of great humanity, and despite his initial rage at having being ousted from his own home, he helps the old Hindu woman settle in. Meanwhile, she shares with Israel and his two friends’ recollections of her village by the Padma River in East Bengal, and thus creates a tableau of a place removed from the conflict of Partition. Her evocation of this rural idyll as a traumatic response at being separated from her world resonates with Israel.

On leaving the house, he confides these feelings to his friend: “Forgive me, Ostad. Hadn’t I said before that I would find no peace till I tear to bits the person who lives in my room now? Did I know then that this wretched old woman would be there?” (11). The men leave the room and stop to listen to the old Hindu lady’s grandson who has been begun singing outside the building. The boy’s beautiful voice lifts their melancholic mood and the text uses this as a dramatic device to communicate both a common Bangla cultural heritage and the sense of nostalgia at its fracture. A deluge of rain falls, and the narrator comments that “It fell in torrents drowning the lone youth’s voice. I felt as if his song had been taken up by millions of voices now!” (15). The noteworthy aspect of Ghatak’s text is how reflective nostalgia, focalized

through the reminiscences of the old Hindu lady and the evocative singing of her grandson, reconfigures the way in which the characters view their relationship with Partition. An engaging with this nostalgia provokes a transcendence of the personal to produce a radical empathy with the other and their suffering. This epiphanic moment can be seen as an understanding of how individual suffering forms a part of a much wider context that lies beyond religious affiliation.

Prafulla Roy's "The Dream Train," originally entitled "Swapner Tren," looks at the lives of a displaced Hindu population from East Bengal. Set at cusp of the 1971 Indo-Pakistan war amidst the escalating tensions that came about due to the demand for autonomy and recognition of Bengali as an official language in East Pakistan, "The Dream Train" focuses its attention on an East Bengali Hindu family who have been living in a North Calcutta slum since the partition of Bengal. The author also migrated from the district of Dhaka to Kolkata during Partition, and he struggled to adapt to his new environment. Roy's personal adversity honed his artistic sensitivity toward disposed populations in general¹. In comparison to "The Road" which gave nostalgia a transcendental energy, "The Dream Train" explores how deracination and being "embroiled in the great middle-class war of survival" (72) creates melancholia and existential paralysis.

Ashok contemplates his father whose body has become skin and bone due to malnourishment. His wife, Namita, ground down by urban life and pregnant once more, whilst his son has jaundice and the family cannot afford medication to treat him. In the face of this struggle, the story's title refers to Ashok's recurring dream whereby he travels by train to his village in East Bengal. The dream is framed as a psychic response to Ashok's pervading sense of economic and cultural displacement, and his unconscious recollections are mediated through a reflective nostalgia that is a manifestation of his estrangement. It is noticeable that the dream journey's primary objective is for Ashok to be reunited with his childhood friends, Rashed, Kamal, and Atikul. These are all Muslim names and, in this respect, Ashok's recurring dream is an unconscious longing to return to the fold of a common Bangla culture.

The narrator tells us that this recurring dream had ceased some thirteen years previously and had now come back. The clues that point to the dreams' sudden reappearance can be found in the text's reference to the political situation of East Pakistan in 1971. We are told that 100,000 people have been killed by Pakistani soldiers in Dhaka and that the people at Ashok's office are demonstrating and organising relief funds. This surge of Bengali nationalism, I suggest, opens up Ashok's old wounds and the losses incurred through Partition. This reactivates his need to return home through his imagination. This dream world, however, soon

fades away in the face of the daily grind of Calcutta, and the narrator concludes that “life could offer him [Ashok] no greater battle than that [struggle]” (72).

Finally, I wish to draw attention to the descriptions of landscapes and rural locations in Bangla fiction. In “The Dream Train,” the narrative describes Ashok’s birthplace, Bajrayogini, in idealized terms. In one particular dream sequence, Ashok is travelling by train through paddy fields that stretches out into the horizon, and the narrator comments that, “As far as one could see the fields were bathed in golden sunshine and flocks of birds were flying overhead, their bodies daubed with gold and sunshine” (62). These descriptions are juxtaposed with the “suffocating alley of north Calcutta” (64) where Ashok’s family now live. The dreamscape creates the sense of a lost world.

In Atin Bandyopadhyay’s “Infidel,” despite the overarching theme of violence and depravity, one can also find short, yet significant, scenes where the rural landscape is also represented in idealized terms. Similar idealizations of the pastoral can be found in *A Life Long Ago*, and these descriptions all form a backdrop to a rural life that both Hindus and Muslims share. Daya and Dada in *A Life Long Ago*, Paran and Hashim in “Infidel,” and Ashok and his friends Rashed, Kamal, and Atikul are all surrounded by a landscape that, itself, becomes a living presence and gains the symbolic weight of a shared Bangla culture that is now lost.

It is important to look at this idealization of the rural and the criticism levied against this. There is the argument that social conflict and injustice are concealed in idealized representations of the past, as configured within the pastoral. The argument is that this literary tradition is “in fact an idealization of feudal values, with the labor and the laborers who support the social order obscured and forgotten” (Natali 20). This, however, refers to a restorative kind of nostalgia and its aforementioned ideological implications. As argued, Bangla fiction employs a reflective form of nostalgia, and it is nuanced in its representations of rural life. The pastoral interacts with the traumatic moment of upheaval rather than underpinning feudal values, and the idealized image of rural Bengal becomes a metonym of unity, projected onto landscape rather than being an ideological tool that masks social inequality.

CONCLUSION

At the beginning of this essay, I referenced how colonial manipulations destined to weaken a nascent liberation movement resulted in the permanent fracture of Bengali society. Questions of caste and class privilege across the religious divide, furthermore, provided fuel to the fratricidal discourses of Partition and resulted in an emotional fracturing of the bonds between Hindus and Muslims. I spoke about how radical Islam played a disruptive role within Bengal society, and while researching for this article, I found a marked inclination within the corpus of historiographic texts toward this reading.

However, I felt it was important to contextualize this idea against a *bhadralok* hegemony that exercised its power within Bengal. Barbara Southard, for example, draws attention to how the Shakta-Vedanta imagery of Bipin Chandra created “a situation conducive to counter-mobilization among Muslims and some lower caste Hindus” and resulted in “communal riots and lasting religious division” (376). Bangla fiction, in this respect, offers nuanced readings on Partition conflict and never adjudicates blame to one side alone. The historiographic background within literary texts and memoir is, however, minimized, and the Bangla literary tradition literature focuses more on the strong affective connections between Hindus and Muslims and of the traumatic fracturing of these bonds. Debjani Sengupta considers that Partition is perceived as “a cosmological occurrence, a loss of a world rather than a loss related to prestige” (195) and, in this light, despite the religious affiliation of Bengali writers, all foreground the destruction of a common culture, unified by language, shared physical spaces and common customs. The Bangla literary tradition considers the Bengali shared linguistic and cultural heritage as being more relevant than the abstract discourses of nationhood. The figure of Jibanananda Das, of Vaidya-Brahmo origin and popularly known as *Rupashi Banglar Kabi* [Poet of Beautiful Bengal] is a pertinent example. Jasodhara Bagchi et al. (2009) document how the appropriation of Das’s poems was central to the *Bhasha Andolôn*, the Bengal Language Movement which resisted Urdu linguistic hegemony in post-independence East Pakistan and asserted Bangladeshi identity through language¹² (195).

Bangla literature demonstrates a tendency to focus on social structures of conviviality and, even when fratricidal violence is explored, it is counterbalanced by narratives of generosity and compassion between Hindus and Muslims. One can detect a utopian energy within Bangla fiction and this point of view, I argue, finds its homologue in Ivan Illich who is also utopian in the way in the way he explores the empowerment of ordinary people through convivial interactions. Fratricidal violence and the end of conviviality, I propose, was explored through the prism of a phenomenological approach in Bangla fiction. This approach privileges

dramatic structures that transmit personal loss and bewilderment overelaborate historiographic backstories.

As a creative device, the reader is immersed into a world of experience which transmits what Husserl defines as the concept of noesis; the process of consciousness directing its attention toward the noema (the disruption of Partition in this case). Memory is another important aspect of Partition narratives, and I have identified how a narrative point of view is informed by what Boym defines as reflective nostalgia which draws attention to the imperfect process of memory and “thrives in *algia*, the longing” (xviii). One of the ways in which literature expresses the loss of a common Bengal culture is through the pastoral, yet whilst the trope of conviviality is present within these settings, writers avoid the over-simplification of the relationship between Hindus and Muslims. This is often done through questions of class, and the reader is invited to dwell upon the lives of an underclass who exist outside history but who suffer the consequences of political agitation. Literature asks us to reconsider our understanding of the binary conflictual model, and the deconstruction of the Hindu-Muslim divide, and the layered readings of the complexities entailed within cross-cultural relationships that Bangla fiction presents us with provides alternative ways of looking at the partition of Bengal.

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NOTES

1. This initial partition lasted until 1911 when Bengal was again reunified.
2. Zamindaris were a system of land revenue collection in India during the Mughal and British colonial periods. The term “zamindar” refers to the landowner or landlord, and the zamindari system was a revenue collection arrangement where land revenue was collected by intermediaries known as zamindars on behalf of the state.
3. One of the principal strategies of the Swadeshi movement was the boycotting of British goods in favour of autochthonous products, plus the banning of Bengalis from trading with British goods. Those who opposed the movement were subjected to various degrees of humiliation, such as social ostracism and other vexations (Sarkar 35-42).
4. Mandal carried out intense field work in East Bengal where he met with Dalit collectives to insist upon their common grievances with Muslims underclass in the face of high caste Hindu oppression (Haq 502). Mandal subsequently served as Pakistan’s first minister of Law and Labour, but returned to West Bengal in 1950 due to ideological differences related to the treatment of Dalits in Pakistan.
5. The Anushilan Samiti revolutionary movement of the first quarter of the twentieth century effectively side-lined Muslims. As Heehs argues in “Revolutionary Terrorism”, whilst the founding members of the Samiti revolutionary group were almost exclusively made up of urban bhadralok who embraced Marxism over a Hindu world-view, communalism soon entered into the grassroots structure of the Samiti movement which resulted in fewer Muslims becoming revolutionaries (162).
6. While Hindus migrated in large numbers from East Bengal to West Bengal, Tripura and Assam, it was “nothing like the exodus of the Punjab and western India” (Haq 502).
7. Tebhaga, which means “three shares” in Bengali, was a demand for a three-share system in the distribution of crops instead of the traditional fifty-fifty share between landlords and peasants. Sharecroppers sought a larger share of the harvest as they believed their efforts in cultivating the land justified a more equitable distribution.
8. There is a discrepancy in the spelling of the novel. Dasgupta and Sengupta refer to it as *Khowabnama*. The book’s title remains in its original Bengali, although Sengupta translates it into “The Dream Chronicles” (207).
9. Jotedar refers to landowners in Bengal, and in particular within the context of sharecropping or tenancy arrangements. These wealthy landowners had significant control over agricultural land and the agrarian economy. Ashraf refers to Muslims of a higher social and economic status. The Jotedar-Ashraf alliance thus makes reference to the intersectionality of economic and social power within a Bengali context.
10. This act has to do with Public Order and Political Agitation.
11. One of the author’s main concerns is how a disenfranchised underclass was invisible within Indian historiography. This worldview informs his narratives on Partition, a pertinent case in hand being his short story “One King Goes and Another King Comes,” originally entitled “Raja Ja Raja Ashe,” and which looks at the life of an impoverished scavenger-fisherman. The narrator observes how the permutation of large tracts of land

between the Hindu and Muslim ruling classes in his village alter nothing as regards social justice.

12. Das's poems mainly focus on pastoral themes set in rural Bengal, and they were interpreted by the Bangladeshi freedom fighters during the 1971 war with Pakistan as a reaffirmation of a Bangla identity.

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